
EFFECT OF SIZING AGENT ON THE INTERFACIAL ADHESION OF CARBON FIBER-REINFORCED POLYAMIDE 6 COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, polyurethane sizing agents adapted in thermoplastic matrix polyamide 6 were prepared. The morphology and microstructure of unsized and sized carbon fibers were characterized by scanning electron microscopy and atomic force microscope. To observe the functional groups of sized carbon fibers, infrared spectra and X-ray photoelectron spectra were performed. Transverse fiber bundle (TFB) test was used to determine interfacial adhesion between carbon fiber and matrix. The results show polyurethane polymer was successfully coated on carbon fiber surface. Sizing remarkably improved interfacial adhesion between carbon fiber and polyamide 6.

1. INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber-reinforced polyamide 6 (PA6) composites have been widely used as structural components in automobile because of its good mechanical properties and low cost. Commercial carbon fibers mostly are applied in epoxy matrix composite materials. It would bring about flaws if commercial carbon fibers are used in polyamide 6 matrix composites. Therefore, it is significant to study sizing agents adapted to the thermoplastic PA6 matrix. Some studies about sizing agent in carbon fiber-reinforced thermoplastic composites have been reported. However, comprehensive study about sizing agent used in carbon fiber-reinforced PA 6 composites is not found.

2. EXPERIMENT

2.1 Materials

Unsize T700 carbon fibers were supplied by ZhongFuShenYing Carbon Fiber Limited Liability Company. PA6 granules were purchased from UBE Engineering Plastic. Aliphatic waterborne polyurethane (PU) polymer was supplied by Jining Baiyi Chemical Co., Ltd. Chemical pure trichloromethane, acetone and distilled water were supplied by Beijing Chemical Works.

2.2 Sizing preparation and sizing process

Polyurethane, the main component of sizing agent, with penetrant, surfactant and other composition was prepared using distilled water into different concentrations. Before used, the sizing solution was mechanical stirred and treated using ultrasonic.

Sizing treatment was carried out by a continuous impregnation process using lab-made equipment shown as in Fig.1. Unsize carbon fibers were pulled through the PU sizing, and subsequently dried in a hot gas oven at 100°C. Then, the sized carbon fibers were rolled up.

2.3 Testing of carbon fiber sizing concentration

Sized carbon fibers were weighed as W_1 by an electronic balance. Then they were desized with Chloroform at 78°C for 24 hours, then ultrasonic cleaned using acetone, dried in the oven at 100°C for 1 h, finally weighed as W_2 . If the carbon fiber sizing concentration is represented as α , it can be calculated by the Eq. (1).

$$\alpha = \frac{W_1 - W_2}{W_2} \times 100\% \quad (1)$$

2.4 Physical characterization of fiber surface

The morphology and microstructure of unsize and sized carbon fibers were characterized by scanning electron microscopy (SEM, JSM7500, Japan) and atomic force microscope (AFM, ICON, America). Ten carbon fiber monofilaments were arranged in parallel on an aluminum block, then were vacuum sputter coated with a thin layer of gold to improve the electrical conductivity for SEM observation. All AFM images were obtained through using the tapping mode in air and the scanning scope was 3×3 μm.

2.4 Chemical characterization of fiber surface

The infrared spectra of sized carbon fibers were performed using a FT-IR spectrometer (Nicolet 6700) to observe the functional groups of the samples. The element composition and interfacial interactions were further studied using an X-ray photoelectron spectra (XPS). XPS experiments were performed on Thermo escalab 250Xi spectrometer equipped with an AlK α (1486.6 eV) X-ray source, and operated at 200W.

2.5 Transverse fiber bundle test

Traditional characterization techniques such as push-out test, fragmentation test, pull-out test and micro droplet test are used to determine the interfacial adhesion at the single filament level between the fiber and matrix. However, it takes too much efforts and time to pick single filament from the fiber tows to make tests complicated. The transverse fiber bundle (TFB) test is a more simple and quick approach.

The approach of preparing transverse fiber bundle specimens is shown as Fig. The molten PA6 was injected into a laboratory-made mold and then stripped to get the pure PA6 dog bone shape sample. The carbon fiber tow was impregnated with molten PA6 under a certain pressure to obtain the prepreg. The appropriate size prepreg was placed in the middle of the PA6 sample inside the mold. Then they were melted again to make combination to obtain TFB specimens.

TFB tests were conducted on a universal test machine with cross-head speed 1mm/min. TFB test for different carbon fiber were tested more than five times. To determine the influence of the sizing on the composites, their tensile fractures were observed by SEM.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Morphology of carbon fibers

The SEM images of unsized and sized carbon fibers are shown in Fig. As we can see, the carbon fiber surface seems to be neat and smooth. However, a thin layer of polymer is on the fiber surface after sizing. It indicates PU polymer was successfully sized on the carbon fiber. Fig shows AFM images for unsized carbon fiber and sized carbon fiber. It is clear that the surface roughness of sized carbon fiber is higher than unsized carbon fiber.

3.2 Surface characteristics of carbon fibers

After sizing treatment, obvious differences were examined by infrared spectroscopy spectra between unsized fibers and sized fibers. The peaks of amide suggest the presence of amide groups. The wide-scan survey XPS spectra of unsized and sized carbon fiber is shown in Fig. After being sized with PU sizing, new peak corresponding to N1s is observed.

3.3 Interfacial adhesion between carbon fiber and matrix

The results of TFB tensile strength of unsized fibers, different sizing content of PU sized fibers and epoxy sized fibers are shown in Fig. 3. What can be seen is that the TFB tensile strength of unsized and epoxy sized carbon fibers is almost the same. It indicated that the interfacial adhesion of epoxy sized carbon fibers reinforced PA6 composites is as low as the unsized carbon fibers. Epoxy sized carbon fibers are not compatible with thermoplastic PA6 composites. Obvious interfacial adhesion improvement can be seen when PU sized carbon fibers were applied in thermoplastic PA6 composites. Less than 1% sizing content, the higher

the sizing content of PU sized fibers is, the better the interfacial adhesion between carbon fiber and PA6 is. However, high sizing content of PU sized fibers could result in fibers stiffness that makes manufacturing process difficult. The SEM images of ensile fractures reveal the reason.

In Fig.8, it can be obviously seen that for the failure mechanism on the fiber surface, adhesive failure is dominated in unsized fiber TFB samples with smooth fiber surface. While, for sized carbon fiber composites, that the fiber surface remained resin and continuity replaced voids between at the interface are visible.

5 FIGURES AND TABLES

Fig.1 Schematic representation of the sizing process.

Fig.2 Schematic diagram for preparation TFB specimens

Fig.3 SEM images for unsized and sized carbon fiber

Fig.4 AFM images for unsized and sized carbon fiber

Fig.5 Wide-scan survey XPS spectra of unsized and sized carbon fiber

Fig.6 TFB test samples and fracture surface.

Fig.7 Results of TFB tensile strength.

Fig.8 SEM for TFB specimen cross section

6. COMCLUSION

The surface functional groups of PU sized fibers were analysed using infrared spectroscopy. By contrast wide-scan survey XPS spectra of unsized and sized carbon fiber, polyurethane polymer was successfully coated on carbon fiber surface is confirmed. SEM and AFM images show sizing slightly changed the surface roughness. TFB results indicted The sizing agent that matches the resin matrix has a significant effect on the interface of composites.

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